

CHALLENGES TO UTILIZATION OF ONLINE ARABIC INFORMATION RESOURCES BY THE ACADEMICS IN AHMADU BELLO UNIVERSITY ZARIA AND BAYERO UNIVERSITY KANO

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ABSTRACT

This study was set out to investigate the challenges to the utilization Online Arabic Information Resources by Academics in the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano. In order to achieve this objective, 4 research questions were formulated and one hypothesis were tested at 0.05. A survey method was employed in the conduct of this study. The entire population was used for this study, which was made up of all the academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies in ABU Zaria and BUK. A well-structure questionnaire was administered to 126 of Academics in both ABU Zaria and BUK with a total of 79 (62.7%) copies returned. The data collected for the study were presented and analyzed using both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Frequency distribution tables, simple percentages were also used for the descriptive statistics while One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypothesis formulated and determine the areas of differences among the Academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies in both Universities. It was discovered that, Slow Internet connectivity in the institution, Erratic power supply, insufficient computer skill and lack of information literacy skill were the major challenges in the utilization of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano respectively. The study recommended that the university library should Provides internet connectivity to each lecturer's office, stable power supply especially in Bayero University Kano,

so as to enable the academics to make optimum utilization of online Arabic Information resources at the comfort of their offices

Keywords: *Online Arabic; Information Resources; Utilization, challenges, Academics; ABU Zaria: BUK*

1. INTRODUCTION

Information is seen as a basic ingredient for personal, social and national development. It's a vital to the overall academic development of university's teaching staff. Thus, it has to be stored and transmitted in both print and electronic devices for access by its customers.

The advancement in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) introduced new dimensions in the generation, acquisition, organization, processing and dissemination of information in virtual environment. The ICTs help information users to search, access and use information regardless of time, distance, location, size and language. The ICTs bring information at the fingertips of information seekers. Libraries use information technology for better services and satisfy diverse user needs (Kattimani and Kamble, 2007). Libraries have transformed into digital and virtual libraries where physical books, journals and magazines, newspapers, theses and dissertations have changed into e-books, e-journals, e-newspapers, e-magazines e-thesis, e-dissertations etc. Online information resources are easily accessed in remote areas. Online information resources solve storage problems and control the flood of information where print sources are being digitised because of the value of information in the life of human endeavor (Swain and Ray, 2009).

2. ARABIC INFORMATION RESOURCES

Arabic Information Resources refer to information sources or resources written in Arabic on various subjects. They are resources that are usually found in Arabic division of the different libraries and information centers. The resources can be in print, non-print and electronic media. They are usually consulted by customers with Arabic language background.

On the other hand, Arabic information resources could be said to consist of documents and other non-book resources in Arabic and English languages provided to satisfy the information needs of users with Arabic language background (Hafez, 2006). Such resources include books of Grammar (Nahwul-wadhihi), Philosophy (Mundhiq) books of Rhetoric (Balagah), Morphology (Sarf) books of literature (Adab), philology (Fiqhul-luggah) Arudiy, Arabic Dictionaries (Qamus) and encyclopedias (Mausuah), Arabic magazines (Mujallah) and newspapers (Jaridah) Book of Sentences analysis (Al'ierab) in print and electronic formats. They may include print journals,

magazines, newspapers, print book, Radio and Television broadcasting. The non prints or Internet based formats include. e-journals, e-books, e-theses, e-newspapers,(HTML or Acrobat pdf), streaming videos, podcasting etc. Some of the Internet based resource may be accessed automatically via a University's IP address or using a given password to restrict access. The purpose of the information resources is to provide knowledge, fact, ideas and opinion on variety of subjects to the users.

3. ONLINE ARABIC INFORMATION RESOURCES

Online information resources are generally in the form of online books, online journals, online magazines, online newspapers, and Internet based resources, e-mail publishing, wireless publishing, and web publishing etc. These are available either through Open Access international donors or commercial vendor's Examples are: Escohost, Hinari, DOAJ, Science direct and SAGE. The online information resources have become a major element of University libraries collections worldwide.

The online Arabic information resources are Arabic sources or resource within Arabic language accessed through Internet, Intranet and network. The online Arabic information resources include online books, online-journals, (HTML or Acrobat PDF), streaming videos, podcasting, etc. Some of the Internet resources are accessible automatically via a University's IP address or by using restricted password for adequate utilization.

Online Arabic information resources, like other online resources, are needed to support the relevant university staffs academic work such as teaching, learning, research and self-development.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Academics are those who are actively involved in teaching learning and research activities. They are involved in teaching, researching, administrating and community development. Academics in any society are seen as the propellers of knowledge because they provide an effective learning environment. They need information resources especially online information resources to support and promote their daily activities. Information is stored, shared, accessed and used properly to support education society. Online information resources have brought about a shift in the provision of library services and information by providing wide access to resources from different parts of the world with ease. Online information resources provide many advantages over print resources such as providing 24x7 access, universal access; saving physical space; ability to linked

from and indexing and abstracting databases; accessibility from the users home, office, or dormitory irrespective of whether or not the physical library is open; the ability to get usage statistics that are not available for print resources and their relative ease of maintenance. Online information resources have become an integral and substantial component of academic library collections worldwide. The resources are regarded as essential for teaching, learning and research activities as well as self and community development (Blecic, Kumar and nand Zhang 2011). Supporting teaching, research and learning activities traditionally becomes a major mission of academic libraries. University library that is to provide access to online information resources in order to enhance information resources utilisation among its customers. However, preliminary observations revealed that most of the citations of the Academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies in writing books, journal articles and conference papers indicate no element of online Arabic citations and no single research was conducted on online Arabic Information Resources. Hence the need of the research on challenges to utilization of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano.

5. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following are the research question the study seeks to answer.

- What types of online Arabic information resources available for use by Academics in ABU Zaria and BUK?
- How do the academics access and utilise the online Arabic information resources available in ABU Zaria and BUK?
- For what purpose do the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano utilised online Arabic information resources?
- What are the challenges to utilisation of online Arabic information resources by the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University, Kano?

6. HYPOTHESES

The research sought to answer the following null hypotheses:

Ho1. There is no significant difference between the types of online Arabic information resources available in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano

7. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To outline the types of online Arabic information resources available for use by

Academics in ABU Zaria and BUK

- To investigate how do the academics utilise the online Arabic information resources available in ABU Zaria and BUK
- To outline the purpose do the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano utilised online Arabic information resources?
- To examine the challenges in the utilisation of online Arabic information resources by the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University, Kano

8. METHODOLOGY

A survey method was employed in the conduct of this study. The total number of 126 (62.7%) Academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano (Arabic Faculty of Art, ABU Zaria, Art and Social Science Education, ABU Zaria, Institute of Education ABU Zaria, Arabic and Islamic Education, ABU Zaria, Centre for Islamic and Legal Studies ABU Zaria, Arabic Department, BUK, Sharia and Islamic studies, BUK) were used for this study. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire; the data collected for the study were presented and analyzed using both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Frequency distribution tables, simple percentages were used for the descriptive statistics while One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypothesis formulated and determine the areas of differences among the Academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies in both Universities.

9. RESULTS

Types of Available Online Arabic Information Resources being Aware of by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano
Types of the Online Arabic Information Resources used by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano

Table below, it was discovered that Brill Online (Journal of Arabic Literature), JAIS Online Database (DOAJ) and Arabica Online, Waqafeeya, Arabwq online and Alslam-L online were the types of online Arabic information resources used by Academics with highest frequency of over 50% responses scores by the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University, Kano respectively, Whereas Al-badr online and Arabwq, Arab e-Marafa (Ebscohost) and The Arabic Paryrology database (Sage OARE) were the types of online Arabic information resources used with least frequency of less than 6.4% responses scores respectively.

However, a further observation from the table indicated that Online Journals of Islamic Studies Religion, Online Islamhouse, Ajurry online, Al-badr online, Ayna.com, Ahlaldeeth online and JAIS online database (DOAJ) were completely not used by the Academic in BUK. This perhaps might be connected to the fact that majority of the Academics teaching Arabic and Islamic Studies may not consider online resources as sources of information for their academic activities. It was also observed that over 61% of the respondent in both ABU Zaria and BUK were not used the available of online Arabic information resources on University Library’s websites. This finding is corroborated by that Talhami, (2009) found that only 18% of academics at the King Faisal Abdulaziz University Library of JIM agreed to make used of Electronic Arabic database, while about 80% knew little about the resources.

Types of Online Arabic Information Resources	Universities			
	ABU Zaria		BU Kano	
	F	%	F	%
Ahlaldeeth online	13	27.7	0	0.0
AIslam-L online	12	25.5	13	40.6
Ajurry online	10	21.3	0	0.0
Al-badr online	4	8.5	0	0.0
Arab e-Marafa (Ebscohost)	4	8.5	5	15.6
Arabic Paryrology database (Sage OARE)	3	6.4	4	12.5
Arabwq online	12	25.5	14	43.8
Arabica online	24	51.1	4	12.5
Askzad online	5	10.6	4	12.5
Ashshamly	9	12.8	6	18.8
Ayna.com	5	10.6	0	0.0
Brill online (Journal of Arabic Literature)	29	61.7	6	18.6
EALL Online	17	36.2	5	15.6
Islamay Online	8	17.0	4	12.5
JAIS Online databases (DOAJ)	24	51.1	0	0.0
Online islamhouse	9	19.1	0	0.0
Online Journals of Islamic Studies Religion	14	29.8	0	0.0
Qardawi.com	6	12.8	6	18.8
Saidul.com	8	17.0	2	6.3

Waqfeya online	10	21.3	12	37.5
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How do the academics access the online Arabic information resources available in the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University, Kano

How do the academics access the online Arabic Universities information resources available

	ABU Zaria		BU Kano	
	F	%	F	%
By direct reading from Net	46	97.9	32	100
By downloading the information resources	38	80.9	32	100
By mere cut and paste	8	17.0	6	18.8
By saving the document in any storage devices	18	38.3	6	18.8
By printing the content of the document	33	70.2	19	59.4
Downloading forwarded document from an email	6	12.8	10	31.3

The table above revealed that Academics Arabic and Islamic studies at ABU Zaria and BUK access the online Arabic information resources through direct reading from the net, downloading the information resource and printing the content of the document with the highest frequency of over 70% and 100% responses scores respectively.

On the other hand, the use of cut and paste, saving the document in the storage devises were found to be the least means of access and use of online Arabic information resources with frequency of less than 20% responses scores. However, from the result, it shows that majority of the respondents prepare reading from the net and downloading the information resource then printing the content of the document.

Means of Accessing Online Arabic Information Resources by the Academics of ABU and BUK

Means of Accessing Online Arabic Information Resources by the Academics of ABU and BUK	UNIVERSITIES			
	ABU Zaria		BU Kano	
	F	%	F	%
Internet (Cable and Wireless)	42	89.4	0	0.0
GSM Network	18	38.3	25	78.1
Internet Café	11	23.4	17	53.1
Modem	32	68.1	25	78.1
Through library website	10	21.3	0	0.0
Search engines	28	59.6	31	96.9

A list of options was provided for the respondents to indicate as many relevant options as possible as shown in the table below.

Means of Accessing Online Arabic Information Resources by the Academics of ABU and BUK

The above table revealed that Internet (Cable and Wires) were the means of accessing online Arabic information resources with highest frequency of 80% responses score by the Academics in ABU Zaria due to availability of internet connectivity in the institution. Whereas internet Café were also another means of accessing online Arabic information resources with the least frequency of less than 23% responses respectively. However at BUK, that GSM Network and personal Modem were the means of accessing online Arabic information resources resource with the highest frequency of Over 70% responses scores by the Academics due to lack of Internet connectivity in the offices and poor ICT finicalities. The study went further to discovered that Over 60% and 90% of the respondents in ABU and BUK access online Arabic information resources through GOOGLE and other search engine instead to search through available online library databases. This finding is supported by earlier finding of Madhusudhan (2007) reveals that most research scholars at Delhi University, used search engines more than subject gateways or Web directories to locate information. This finding is not agreed by Abdul Mannan Khan (2009) noted that a majority of research scholars and Faculty members of JMI and JNU Universities were able to access online database through central universities library website. This shows that there is need for both Universities library to organize more training to their academics especially those teaching Arabic and Islamic on the use of online database available.

Purposes to Utilization of Online Arabic Information Resource by the Academics in ABU Zaria and BUK

The table revealed the response of the respondents on the reasons/purpose for utilization online Arabic information resources that research activities , thesis writing, lecture note, teaching, preparing writing for publication were the major reasons for the use of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in ABU Zaria and BUK. This finding corroborates the finding of Talhami, (2009) reports Arabic database are used for research purposes, about one-quarter to one third used it to prepare lectures and gain subject knowledge.

Purpose of access and use of online Arabic Information Resources by the respondents of ABU Zaria and BUK	Universities			
	ABU Zaria		BU Kano	
	F	%	F	%
Research activities	40	85.1	32	100
Paper writing for publication	24	51.1	23	71.9
Teaching	27	57.4	15	46.9
Seminar/workshop presentation	21	44.7	12	37.5
Self-development	8	17.0	1	3.1
Consultancy service	16	34.0	2	6.3
Community development	5	10.6	6	18.8
Lecture Note	32	68.1	24	75.0
Thesis/ Dissertation writing	37	78.7	25	78.1

Challenges to Utilization of Online Arabic Information Resources by the Academic of ABU Zaria and BUK

Challenges faced by the respondents of ABU and BUK in accessing the online Arabic information resources available.	Universities			
	ABU Zaria		BU Kano	
	F	%	F	%
Not computer literate	33	70.2	24	75.0
Slow Internet connectivity in the institution	46	97.9	31	96.9
Erratic power supply	46	97.9	29	90.6
Poor ICT facilities	39	83.0	32	100
Lack of access to Internet connectivity in the office	37	78.7	30	93.8
Insufficient access to needed journals	32	68.1	31	96.9

From Table Shown that slow Internet connectivity in the institution, Erratic power supply, insufficient computer skill and lack of information literacy skill were the major challenges in the utilization of online Arabic information resources with highest frequency of over 85% responses scores by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano

respectively. Whereas, poor ICT facilities and lack of Internet connectivity in the office were the major challenges in the utilization of online Arabic information resources with highest frequency of 95% and 100% responses scores by the Academics at Bayero University Kano. The prevalence of these challenges was also reported in similar studies such as Abdullahi and Haruna (2008) who found out that lack of basic knowledge of ICT is the second major constraint after the problem of erratic power supply to the use of electronic resources in the university libraries in Nigeria. The result falls in line with Hafeez (2010) identified various problems the users face while using Arabic electronic resources. Slow internet connectivity, Poor ICTs facilities, lack of access to low cost printers in the library, using advanced search strategy of most databases, and lack of awareness of most of the e resources are significant contributors for the low patronage of customer

HYPOTHESIS ONE

Analysis of variance on the types of available online Arabic information resources in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano

Group Statistics

COLLEGE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	DF	t-value	P	Decisions
ABU ZARIA	47	4.8085	3.24130	.47279	77	3.307	.001	Significant
BUK KANO	32	2.8125	1.28107	.22646				

Table shows the analysis of variance on the type of available online Arabic information resources in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano at (P<0.05) level of significance. From the table, the observed T- value of 3.307 is greater than the P critical value of .001 at the same degree of freedom. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. It can therefore be concluded that there is a difference between the types of online Arabic information resources available in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano

10. SUMMARY OF MAJOR FINDINGS

Based on the data collected and analyzed for this study, the following are the major findings:

Brill Online (Journal of Arabic Literature), JAIS Online Database (DOAJ) and Arabica Online, Waqafeeya, Arabwq online and Alslam-L online were the types of online Arabic

information resources used by Academics by the academics in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University, Kano respectively,

that Academics Arabic and Islamic studies at ABU Zaria and BUK utilised the online Arabic information resources through direct reading from the net, downloading the information resource and printing the content

Internet (Cable and Wires) were the means of accessing online Arabic information resources by the Academics in ABU Zaria due to availability of internet connectivity in the institution

that research activities , thesis writing, lecture note, teaching, preparing writing for publication were the major reasons for the use of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in ABU Zaria and BUK.

Slow Internet connectivity in the institution, Erratic power supply, insufficient computer skill and lack of information literacy skill were the major challenges in the utilization of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano respectively.

There is no significant difference between the types of online Arabic information resources available in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and Bayero University Kano.

11. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it could be concluded that Slow Internet connectivity in the institution, Erratic power supply, insufficient computer skill and lack of information literacy skill were the major challenges in the utilization of online Arabic information resources by the Academics in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and Bayero University Kano respectively, this led to under- utilization of the resources. Therefore, the study recommended that the university library should Provides internet connectivity to each lecturer's office, stable power supply especially in Bayero University Kano, so as to enable the academics to make optimum utilization of online Arabic Information resources at the comfort of their offices.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, A &Harun S.A. (2008). use of e-resources among postgraduate student at the Islamic University in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Journals of Academic librarianship*, 23(1), 69-75.
- Hafeez. B, A. (2006), availability and use of Arabic databases by research scholars of King Faisal Abdul-Azeez library, Jami'atul Islam Madina, *Libri*, 49(1), 1-9.

- Ibrahim A. E. (2006), Use and perception of online databases in Islamic private Universities, *Libri*, 54(1), 18-29
- Kattimani PS, Kamble V. T. (2007). Bannari Amman Institute of Technology. Tahlil Nadu. *Indian J. Inf. Sci. Sci. Serv.* 1(1), 1-2.
- Kinengyire A. A (2007), The effect of information literacy on the utilization of e- resources in Uganda. *The electronic library*, 25(3), pp. 238-341.
- Khalid, M (2011). Utilisation of Arabic information resources in College and Islamic University in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Brill online*, 1 (2), PP.15-19, Available at:
URL:<https://www.brill.jjjdal.org.56b3cba1-a-62cb3a1a-s>
- Lutchumanan B, and TalhamiA. (2011). Electronic Resources Usage in Academic and Research institutions in Tanzania. *Information Development*, 21(4).
- Madhusudan, M. (2008). Use of UGCinformat e-journal by research scholars and student of University of Delhi, Delhi. *Library Hi tech*, 26 (3), 369-386.
- Talhami, T. (2009). Awareness and use of electronic Databases by postgraduate's student in king Faisa Abdulazizz University. *Brill online*, 1(2), 15-19.
- Ojedokum, A.A. and Owolabi, E.O. (2003). Internet access competence and use of internet for teaching and research by University of Botswana Academic staff. *African Journal of library, Archive and Information Science*, 13 (1), 43-53.
- Ray S, Walavalkar P. (2009). Re-inventing the corporate library: A success story of best practices in TCS libraries. International conference proceedings. In *Shaping the future of special libraries: Beyond Boundaries* (pp. 517-523.). New Delhi: Ane books Pvt.
- Zhang, Ye and Lui. (2011). Electronic databases Usage in India scenario, *Libri*, 21 (4).